

TWINNED
By Stars

TWINNEDbySTARS

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

**D5.1 DISSEMINATION &
COMMUNICATION PLAN**

WP5 DISSEMINATION

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORS**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	04/12/2023	Draft version sent to Steering Committee for comments	Sara Rebollo Ramírez, Beatrice Avagnina
1.0	21/12/2203	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the Steering Committee	Silvia Pérez Palomo, Sara Rebollo Ramírez, Beatrice Avagnina
2.0	21/01/2025	Updated version of the Plan	Silvia Pérez Palomo, Beatrice Avagnina

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	TWINNEDBySTARS
Project Title	Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs
Type of action	EMFAF Project Grants
Topic	EMFAF-2023-PIA-FLAGSHIP-5-OR
Project Start Date	01/10/2023
Project Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP5 – COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION
Deliverable	D5.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN
Due Date	31/12/2023
Submission Date	21/01/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	CE (CONSULTA EUROPA)
Version	2.0
Status	Final version
Author(s)	Sara Rebollo Ramírez, Silvia Pérez Palomo, CE Beatrice Avagnina
Reviewer(s)	Steering Committee members

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Version History	1
Deliverable Information	2
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. CONTEXT ANALYSIS	7
1.1 THE PROJECT	7
1.2 THE CONSORTIUM	7
1.3 TWINNEDBYSTARS COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION WORK PACKAGE	8
2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION APPROACH	9
2.1. EC RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO RESULTS	9
2.2 INTELLECTUAL AND PROPERTY RIGHTS	10
3. TARGET GROUPS	11
3.1 IDENTIFICATION	11
3.2 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	12
3.3 TAILORED COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	13
4. COMMUNICATION AND GUIDELINES	15
4.1 INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION	15
4.2 PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY	16
4.2.1 LOGOTYPE	16
4.2.2 COLOURS AND TYPOGRAPHY	17
4.3. INFORMATION LEAFLETS, POSTERS, AND ROLL-UP BANNER	18
4.4 WEBSITE	18
4.5 SOCIAL MEDIA	19
4.5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA PLAN	20
4.6 NEWSLETTER	21
4.6.1 CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT AND GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION	22
4.6.2 INDIVIDUAL RIGHTS and consent	22
4.7 PRESS RELEASE	23
4.8 VIDEOS	23
5. EVENTS AND CONFERENCES	24
5.1 ORGANISATION OF EVENTS	24
5.1.1 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT EVENTS	24
5.1.2 TRAINING EVENTS	25
5.1.3 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE	25

5.2 ASSISTANCE TO OTHER EVENTS	25
5.2.1 MAPPING OF EVENTS	25
5.2.2 REGIONAL / NATIONAL / EU EVENTS.....	26
6. PRESS OFFICE	26
7. MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS.....	27
8. SYNERGIES AND NETWORKING	28
8.1 OBJECTIVES AND PRESENTATION.....	28
8.2 SISTER PROJECTS.....	28
8.3 PARTNERS' NETWORKING ACTIVITIES	29
9. CONTINGENCY PLANS	30
10. MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES.....	33
10.1 MONITORING OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES.....	33
10.2 MONITORING ON PARTNERS' DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES.....	34
10.3 EVALUATION OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	35
11. COMMUNICATION TOOLS	35
11.1 ROLL UP	36
11.2 LEAFLET	36
11.3 WEBSITE.....	37
11.4 SOCIAL MEDIA.....	43
11.5 HASHTAGS.....	43
CONCLUSIONS.....	44

ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
DM	Dissemination Manager
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of the Action
OR	Outermost Region
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IM	Innovation Management
DMP	Data Management Plan
EIA	Evaluation and Impact Assessment

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Dissemination & Communication (D&C) Plan is a comprehensive guide for the project's communication and dissemination activities that encompasses both internal and external communication. Moreover, it defines key communication messages to be shared and used by all project partners, communication targets to be reached, communication tools tailored to the specific needs of each target group, calendar of activities, events to be attended, monitoring and reporting of D&C activities.

This Plan also presents the practical steps for the monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities under section 10 "Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities".

1. CONTEXT ANALYSIS

1.1 THE PROJECT

The aim of **TWINNEDBySTARS** is converting European Outermost Regions (ORs) into an internationally recognized maritime ecotourism destination, which exploits benefits of tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.

The project builds on the success of previous projects in the Macaronesian region, which have built networks and methodological frameworks to codesign and tune up transformational marine eco-tourism products and activities, involving SMEs located on different islands. Onboard marine environmental education, navigation, respectful sighting, and start light attributes are examples of good practices that combined with unpublished interpretative experiences of marine sighting have generated highly satisfactory tourist experiences and higher environmentally responsible behaviour of SMEs and tourists. **TWINNEDBySTARS** aims to scale out these experiences at the level of the EU ORs, while fostering the uptake of green and digital innovation by these communities, strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building, and opportunities for co-creation.

1.2 THE CONSORTIUM

The **TWINNEDBySTARS** project is managed by a consortium of 10 partners and 1 affiliated entity from 4 countries (Spain, Portugal, Belgium and France) ranging from universities and research institutes to governmental institutions and small enterprises (SMEs) related to maritime and nautical eco-tourism.

Table 1. **TWINNEDBySTARS** Consortium

Partner No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC-TIDES	ES
1.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT ULPGC	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Asociación Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
4	Océano de Experiencias SL	NAUTIC OCEAN	ES
5	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas	CETECIMA	ES
6	Associação MarinaFunchal	MARINA FUNCHAL	PT
7	Associação Comercial E Industrial Do Funchal	ACIF-CCIM	PT
8	Secretaria Regional do Mar e das Pescas	DRPM AZORES	PT
9	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	CTM	FR
10	European Boating Industry	EBI	BE

1.3 TWINNEDBYSTARS COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION WORK PACKAGE

The effect and impact of TWINNEDBySTARS will rely greatly on effective communication. The project needs to engage with a different set of actors such as scientists and technicians, entrepreneurs and investors, policymakers, and other public and private stakeholders as well as citizens. WP5 will lead the project’s communication and dissemination efforts in close synergy with WP1 which foresees the definition and management of a dedicated stakeholder engagement plan for the project, WP2 which aims to build a strong community of enterprises across the 4 regions in order to build and implement an effective capacity building programme, and WP3 which will foster and maximize the exploitation opportunities of the TWINNEDBySTARS new products and new nautical tourism experiences.

The WP5 D&C Plan will cover both internal and external communication and define a) key communication messages to be shared and used by all project partners; b) communication targets to be reached; c) communication tools tailored to the specific needs of each target group; d) calendar of activities e) events to be attended and f) monitoring and reporting of D&C activities.

This WP responds to all project objectives since its aims at disseminating and transferring the outputs and results of all TWINNEDBySTARS activities to its key stakeholders. Specific objectives of this WP are:

1. To give visibility to the project and raise awareness among the general public
2. To support stakeholder engagement activities
3. To support knowledge transfer through scientific and non-scientific publications, organization of trainings events
4. To connect with a wide network of EU projects, initiatives to exchange experience and promote R&I activities
5. To ensure efficient internal communication between partners and follow up their activities.

This deliverable “D5.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan” is the key starting point for WP5 communication and dissemination activities. It will be considered as a living document, executed throughout the duration of the project and internally reviewed and updated upon needs and progression of the project activities.

These are all the tasks included in this D&C plan:

Table 2. TWINNEDBySTARS tasks.

List of tasks		Responsible partner(s)
T5.1	Development of the D&C Plan.	CE
T5.2	Dissemination activities.	CE & EBI
T5.3	Awareness raising activities and outreach to society.	CE

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION APPROACH

This paragraph presents a set of five principles upon which the TWINNEDBySTARS Dissemination and Communication Plan has been built:

- **Adaptability.** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication and dissemination activities need to be adaptable to the project's various research themes, stakeholder communities and project progress. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users. The targets groups will be specified in Section 3 "Target groups".
- **Flexibility.** Communication needs to be flexible and open to creating a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
- **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** TWINNEDBySTARS needs to be able to speak to a variety of actors and stakeholders with different backgrounds and objectives in mind. To achieve this, the project must formulate key messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication using laymen's language).
- **Exploitation of synergies.** To maximize the impact and efficiency of exploitation an extensive network of external collaborations of project partners will be used, and opportunities sought to join and contribute to existing networks and platforms which have relevant remits.
- **Gender sensitive and inclusive communication.** Certain words and images we use to communicate must be considered carefully since they can perpetuate images of socially prescribed gender roles and behaviors. TWINNEDBySTARS will adopt a non- hierarchical and nonpatronizing style, to promote gender-sensitive communication, identify gender stereotypes and use a fair and balanced representation of women and men in communication.

2.1. EC RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO RESULTS

Dissemination of results is a contractual obligation for projects funded under the EMFAF programme. The partners must, therefore, conduct various dissemination activities through different means including electronic tools such as project websites, e-publications, information platforms, and promotional material such as leaflets, press releases, posters, as well as various events including stakeholder workshops, thematic meetings, and conferences at national and European levels. At the same time, dissemination activities shall be compatible with the protection of intellectual property rights, confidentiality obligations and the legitimate interests of the owner(s) of the foreground, as stated in the Grant Agreement.

The granting authority has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries on a royalty-free basis. More information regarding this can be found in Article 16 the Annotated Model Grant Agreement or at TWINNEDBySTARS's own Grant Agreement (GA).

To implement dissemination and exploitation activities effectively, it is thus essential to have a good understanding of the definitions of the respective terms and concepts within the context of EMFAF projects. Project partners are therefore encouraged to consult the following key documents and online sources for the definition of various terms and description of various procedures and processes as well as the respective roles and responsibilities of each party.

- TWINNEDBySTARS's GA including Annex 1 – Description of the Action (DoA), in particular description of WP5; and Terms and Conditions of the Grant Agreement, in particular chapter 4 Grant Implementation, section 2 Rules for carrying out the action, articles 16 & 17.
- TWINNEDBySTARS's Consortium Agreement (CA), in particular section 8 (Results), section 9 (Access Rights), and section 10 (Non-disclosure of Information).

Furthermore, as per Article 17 of the GA, project's materials must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

The emblem can be found in the following [LINK](#). It must remain distinct and separate. It cannot be modified by adding other visuals. When displayed with other logos, it must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Any relevant communication or dissemination activity related to the action must indicate the following disclaimer:

"Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

Partners should keep track of all their dissemination and exploitation activities and report to WP5 Leader: Consulta Europa (CE). The WP leader will then report the statistics to the EC at the reporting stages. CE is required to report any publication and dissemination activities on the Grant Management System of the EU Funding and Tenders Portal.

2.2 INTELLECTUAL AND PROPERTY RIGHTS

The TWINNEDBySTARS Consortium recognises the importance of managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Innovation Management (IM) in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, adhering to EMFAF programme principles. The

rules for the utilisation of foreground and background knowledge, as well as for the handling of sensitive and confidential information are defined in the TWINNEDBySTARS Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

Dedicated tasks have therefore been included in WP3 under Task 3.5 Evaluation and impact assessment. The EIA will also draft business plans for the market penetration of the outputs. The CA will detail all aspects concerning IPR-related matters. The IM will play a pivotal role in ensuring an effective and end-user driven innovation management. This will include the management of partners' background used for the project implementation, as well as the protection and regulation of generated Foreground.

During the project implementation, the GA, with the supervision and strong collaboration of the IM, will monitor the produced results and identify any specific issue that requires prior agreement among partners. The GA will also undertake any needed measure to identify results that are suitable for commercial exploitation and identify proper exploitation strategies to be proposed to the IM. Decisions related to IPR issues will be taken by the GA. The harmonization and integration of data and indicators will be a key functional activity to enable the application of methods and tools and will require an appropriate Data Management Plan (DMP, under the leadership of CE) to be periodically refined and completed in order to establish data-sharing policies and regulate access rights for the databases, coherently with the CA rules and the DMP.

3. TARGET GROUPS

3.1 IDENTIFICATION

One of TWINNEDBySTARS’s key objectives is the implementation of an inclusive process, by engaging stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, prioritising such as scientists and technicians, entrepreneurs, policymakers, and other public and private stakeholders as well as citizens.

During the project, a stakeholder’s identification will be carried out through different tasks, mainly at WP1 and WP5. For this purpose, a mapping of actors (task 1.1) of the quadruple helix and a Stakeholder Engagement Plan will be carried out previously to ensure a wide representation of these stakeholders as target groups in the communication and dissemination of the project.

Initial activities will be carried out to set the basis for the next project activities, including analysing the existing cooperation networks in the field of maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs in order to identify and engage the most relevant stakeholder networks in line with the TWINNEDBySTARS initiative. CMC will lead WP1 for the sustainability of the cooperation established in the framework of TWINNEDBySTARS, under its experience as leader of the Macaronesian Maritime Marine Alliance (A3M) and partner of the Nautical Cooperation Network NAUTICOM).

TWINNEDBySTARS will target representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model, recognizing four major actors in the innovation system:

Table 3. Target groups description.

TARGET GROUP	DESCRIPTION
Science stakeholders	Include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to greening activities and innovation. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists. At local, national, intergovernmental, and EU levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Policy makers	Representatives of private or public institutions of local, national and global governance, promotion, environmental management and regulation of

	tourism and nautical activities. Directorates-General (RTD, CLIMA, ENER, ENV, MARE), the JRC, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency; the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group.
Industry	All companies related to nautical and marine tourism. It includes those offering sports and recreational activities at sea. It also includes enterprises selling nautical equipment, charter services, whale watching, nautical schools, and the ports and marinas offering berths and other services to yachts.
Society/public	Citizen science activities will be promoted as for the first group, environmental organizations, local action groups, and other types of associations will be reached to provide them with comprehensive information on TWINNEDBySTARS solutions and to foster social acceptance.

3.2 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

In Table 4, the communication channels and types of information to be shared with each stakeholder are defined:

Table 4. Target groups communication details.

TARGET GROUP	COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	TYPE OF INFORMATION
Science stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open-access publications Conference presentations Social media and website Events / workshops Journals Specialised and scientific media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project description and updates Project scientific publications Project results
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint sessions/events Seminars, roundtables, etc Newsletter Media (press releases) Policy feedback reports 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results Project description and updates Project impact Advantages of the prototype
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Events and trainings / workshops (Social) Media and direct emailing Website Synergies Factsheets Promotional materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results Business/exploitation plan
Society/public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website and newsletters (Social) Media Focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project description and updates Project publications

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events • Press releases on local media • Promotional materials and factsheets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project impact assessment
--	---	---

These groups might change depending on the stakeholder’s identification carried out at the beginning of the project.

3.3 TAILORED COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

An effective strategy of D&C should adapt its key messages to each type of audience/stakeholder targeted in order to achieve the maximum impact and engagement. At the same time, each project outputs should be appropriately channeled to achieve their highest exploitation levels. The Table 5 tailors the D&C and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder.

Table 5. Tailored D&C and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder.

TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	D&C ACTIVITIES	ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES
Science stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverables • Shorter research briefs might be produced • Prepare posters to be shared at scientific conferences • Events / Webinars • Peer review publication • Zenodo community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propose participation in webinars to present specific topics • Workshops/focus groups
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of policy briefs from the deliverables • Events / Webinars • National & International Conferences held for end users and policy makers • Policy briefs in national languages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars to get inputs in order to shape project activities and expected results • Video interviews • Workshop/roundtables
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National conferences / events / workshops & trainings • Specific type of events • Briefs and factsheets by e-mail, through newsletters and social media • Videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video interviews to promote their activities • Focus groups • Webinars Conferences
Society/public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National conferences /events • Social media and press • Leaflets • Videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars • Round-tables • Discussions Focus groups

Table 6 relates the deliverables that will be disseminated publicly to each targeted audience.

Table 6. Projects deliverables and their targeted dissemination groups.

WP No.	No.	Deliverable name	Date	Target audience
1	D1.1	Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs and mapping of actors in the quadruple helix	Aug 24	*Project partners
	D1.2	Stakeholder engagement plan	March 24	*Research community
	D1.3	Report on enhancement of digitalisation and circular economy	Oct 25	*Industry representatives, investors *Societal actors *Policy and decision-makers
	D1.4	Internationalisation plan	Sept 24	*Project partners *Policy and decision makers
	D1.5	Legacy Plan	Sept 26	
2	D2.1	Training programme methodology	Apr 25	*Project partners *Policy and decision makers
	D2.2	Report on the conclusions of the training	Dec 25	
	D2.3	Report on capacity building programme's sustainability and exploitation	July 26	
3	D3.1	Report on analysis of available coastal and maritime tourism products and development sites	Feb 25	*Industry (SMEs, investors, etc.)
	D3.2	Co-creation workshops on tourism product(s) programme	Dec 24	*Research community (researchers, PhD students)
	D3.3	Report on the product developed including a marketing & business plan	Apr 25	*Policy and decision makers
	D3.4	Joint commercialisation agreement	May 25	*Research community (researchers, PhD students)
	D3.5	Report on evaluation and impact assessment	July 26	*Project partners

				*Policy and decision makers
4	D4.1	Management Plan	Nov 23	*Project partners
	D4.2	Quality Assurance Plan	Jan 24	
	D4.3	Risk management Plan	Apr 24	
	D4.4	Policy Feedback Report 1	Mar 25	
	D4.5	Policy Feedback Report 2	Aug 26	
	D4.6	Data Management Plan	Mar 24	
5	D5.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Dec 23	* Research community (researchers, PhD students) *Industry Representatives, Investors *Society (citizens, public, civil society organisations) *Decision makers
	D5.2	Project factsheet	Dec 23	
	D5.3	Report on D&C activities 1	Sep 24	
	D5.4	Report on D&C activities 2	Sep 25	
	D5.5	Report on D&C activities 3	Aug 26	
	D5.6	Report on awareness raising activities and outreach to society	Sep 26	

In addition to the deliverables listed in the table above, at least one **peer reviewed publication** will be launched within the framework of TWINNEDBySTARS. This document will be led by the coordinating entity (as academic partner) ULPGC with the active contribution of the rest of the consortium.

4. COMMUNICATION AND GUIDELINES

To standardize communication and dissemination activities, several communication tools and materials have been developed. This section will collect them and guide project partners on how to implement them.

4.1 INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

The **internal communication** needed for the correct dissemination and communication of the project will include a set of various internal communication activities:

- An internal shared folder will contain all project details and documents related to WP5. This can be found under the folder 4.Work Packages > WP5 Dissemination & Communication.
- Mailing lists will be created allowing easy contact with work package leaders, steering committee, and other external stakeholders groups.
- Teams will be the virtual meeting platform.
- Friday email sent regularly to the consortium to recap on latest important project developments.

External communication activities will aim at delivering clear messages to the project stakeholders through a set of targeted communication tools and make a strong and impactful contribution to the project's high-level objectives. TWINNEDBySTARS will target representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model, recognizing four major actors in the innovation system: **science, policy, industry, and society**. Even if some stakeholders belong to several categories an initial identification and classification will be done to define the best communication channels and tools for each category. All four Quadruple Helix categories are equally important for TWINNEDBySTARS' long-term success.

4.2 PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

One of the foundational elements key to effective communication and widespread dissemination of project outcomes is the establishment of a robust visual identity. A well-defined visual identity will play a pivotal role in increasing awareness of the TWINNEDBySTARS project.

TWINNEDBySTARS has meticulously crafted a strong and coherent visual identity to facilitate the efficient dissemination and communication of the project results. The initial and central focus in establishing a consistent visual identity involves the development of the project logo, along with the determination of primary colours and stylistic elements to be consistently applied throughout all project documents and materials. This approach serves to define the project's distinct identity and ensure its recognizability across various contexts.

4.2.1 LOGOTYPE

The logo presented below in Figure 1 was collaboratively developed by CE, incorporating feedback and suggestions from all project partners. Following a series of iterations and options, the logo was chosen through a survey conducted within the Consortium.

Figure 1. TWINNEDBySTARS logotype.

The intricately crafted TWINNEDBySTARS logo serves as a visual embodiment of the project's multifaceted goals, weaving together the key elements of marine tourism in Outermost Regions (ORs), circular economy, innovation, digital transition, and internationalization. The thoughtful design emphasises two pivotal components at the heart of the project's vision.

At the forefront, the sailboat stands tall and proud, symbolising the exploration and celebration of marine and maritime eco-tourism within the Outermost Regions. Its presence encapsulates the essence of navigating through the unique landscapes and rich biodiversity these regions offer.

A celestial dance unfolds above the sailboat, where four stars in striking red hues punctuate the deep blue background. These stars not only illuminate the night sky but also represent the interconnectedness of TWINNEDBySTARS' objectives. Each star is a beacon guiding the project's commitment to open and social innovation, fostering collaboration and shared knowledge among partners and stakeholders. The stars symbolise the vast potential for innovation and digital transition within the project, where ideas twinkle and align to illuminate a path towards sustainable tourism practices.

Encircling the composition, the prominent blue circle signifies the circular economy, a core tenet of TWINNEDBySTARS. This encompassing ring represents the project's dedication to creating a closed-loop system where resources are utilised efficiently and sustainably, mirroring the cyclical patterns found in nature. The circular economy is not only a design element but a foundational principle, demonstrating the project's commitment to responsible and eco-friendly practices.

4.2.2 COLOURS AND TYPOGRAPHY

The chosen colours for the visual identity, red and blue, were selected to reflect the dynamic and interconnected nature of marine and celestial elements, further reinforcing the project's thematic focus. This deliberate colour scheme aims to evoke a sense of vibrancy and cohesion that resonates with the project's core themes as displayed in figure 2.

Figure 2. TWINNEDBySTARS's colors and typography.

Regarding typography, the main font selected for all communication materials is Montserrat, known for its modern and clean aesthetic. This choice aligns with the project's commitment to presenting information in a clear and visually appealing manner, enhancing overall readability and brand consistency.

For secondary typography used in documents to ensure readability, the project has opted for Open Sans. This font was chosen for its balance between professionalism and legibility, contributing to the seamless consumption of information in project-related documents.

4.3. INFORMATION LEAFLETS, POSTERS, AND ROLL-UP BANNER

To promote the main ideas of this project, a **leaflet** will be used. A template will be developed in the format of a booklet as key promotional material. The leaflet will be in a standard A4 size, folded in 2. This material will provide information on what are the challenges facing the project, what are the objectives it intends to achieve and what are the work packages that constitute the work plan. It will also briefly explain what the vision of the project is and include the logos of the 11 members of the consortium (10 partners and 1 affiliated entity). It will be used and disseminated by the partners during relevant events and meetings (each partner being responsible for printing the leaflets). The digital version of the leaflet will be available in the internal communication channels of TWINNEDBySTARS.

A standardized **roll-up** will be developed, the measures will be 85 cm x 200cm. The roll-up design will convey key messages, branding, funding, the EU emblem, and promotional information about the project such as the website and the social media channels. The roll-up will be made available to be printed and used by every partner to assist any on-site event. This roll-up design may also be used digitally to promote the project on different websites, platforms, digital newspapers and social media channels. Project posters, postcards, and other relevant promotional material to be used in dissemination activities will be produced within this task. These materials will be created to draw the attention of the audience to the TWINNEDBySTARS project during different events.

A general template of **PPT** (Power Point Presentation) with the image and the logo of the project has been designed by CE and shared with all partners. This PPT must be used when presenting all kinds of information about the project activities used for internal and external public. This template is available in the *Teams* folder: General > 4. Work Packages > WP5 Dissemination and Communication.

4.4 WEBSITE

The TWINNEDBySTARS website will be created and developed in the first months of the project and filled out with all relevant information about the project and the consortium.

The website's structure is as follows:

HOME. The first tab presents the visual identity, the name of the project and a brief description.

- The Newsletter box to subscribe to the newsletter.

ABOUT. In the second tab there will be the main information regarding the project Objectives. Objectives of the project and expected impacts are presented.

- Objectives. Objectives of the project and expected impacts are presented.
- Work packages. Inside the project tab one can find all Work packages explained with pictures and results updates

- Sister projects. This section will consist of useful information regarding relevant sister projects and initiatives.

RESULTS. In the third tab (which will be visible once first results are attained), there will be information more specific of the project results including public deliverables:

- Results. The results are the most important part of the website, where the work of TWINNEDBySTARS is shown. First, dissemination and communication materials will be shared. Later, when Deliverables are submitted and approved, those that are meant to be public will be shared here. Moreover, additional sections such as results from WP3 co-creation workshops will be added as long as the project progresses and generates outputs. Furthermore, WP5 will assess the possibility of adding a dedicated section (within the Results webpage, or as a separate, standalone section) to showcase the members of the project community, namely companies engaged in WP2 and WP3.

NEWS & EVENTS. The fourth tab will consist of the news and events related to the project:

- TWINNEDBySTARS news. This section will consist of news on TWINNEDBySTARS events and results.
- What others are saying. This other section will show what other media is saying about the project.
- Social media feed. There will be a section solely on social media, showing the last tweets and posts.

PARTNERS. The fifth tab will consist of information regarding each partner (their logos, descriptions, and institutional websites and social media).

CONTACT. Finally, the last tab will contain a contact section with an online form to be filled in. Also, this section will provide contact information and a legal warning to let users know how their data is used in case they decide to provide it (also by subscribing to the newsletter).

The website will be accessible at the following address: <https://TWINNEDBySTARS.eu/>.

The website will be developed in English to be accessible to any kind of international and EU stakeholders. Its purpose is to act as “vitrine” of the project and to get in touch with interested parties since the very beginning of the project.

The website, like other D&C materials, will be a living space, that will be maintained, updated and further developed throughout the project to be as active and attractive as possible. It is for this reason that the website includes a section where to read regular news articles that will be posted and another section with all social media platforms integrated. **All project partners will support providing information for the publication of news on the website to CE.**

4.5 SOCIAL MEDIA

For communication purposes, a set of social media accounts have been developed, each targeting different audiences. Social media will be set up to promote Account via trending hashtags, live tweeting from high profile events. TWINNEDBySTARS can be followed on Twitter/X, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn:

- The [Facebook](#) page where all project partners and individuals can follow the page and check the news and updates of the project.

- The [Instagram](#) account to share images of the events, keep posted on a more frequent basis than other social media, engage followers with activities and questionnaires and share information.
- The [Twitter/X](#) account is used to share news links and keep people interested in the news of the project. It also works to get updates from other projects and actors valuable in TWINNEDBySTARS 's field.
- The [LinkedIn](#) profile is a more professional account to engage partners and strategic target groups as policy and decision-makers as well as EU projects and initiatives.

All these accounts have been created and will be updated regularly during the duration of the project with information on project results, partners, events organized, interviews, other relevant project's events, results and information.

4.5.1 SOCIAL MEDIA PLAN

A social media plan will be developed according to the tasks and/or activities performed under every work package of the project. In addition to this, content will also be published related to the fields of marine-based eco-tourism, circular economy, digitalization, innovation, blue economy, other sister projects, and so on. Mainly two lines of posts will regularly be published:

- Activities performed (Project results and updates)
- General Content (events, news, and other sister projects).

The social media plan will include specific campaigns according to vital milestones of the project.

Whenever possible, social media releases from the official accounts of the project will tag and make reference to the partners' own medial channels, which will act as multipliers of TWINNEDBySTARS news and posts. Social media accounts of the project partners are the following:

Table 7. List of the partner's social media.

Part ner	Facebook	X	Instagram	LinkedIn
ULP GC	@ULPGC @Instituto Universitario Tides	@ULPGC @INSTITUTOTI DES	@ULPGC	@ULPGC @TidesInstitute @Catedraunesco turismo
FPC T	@FPTCULPGC	@FPTCULPGC	@FPCTULPGC	@FPTCULPGC
CE	@CE	@CE	@CE	@CE
CMC	@CMC	@CMC	@CMC	@CMC
NAU TIC OCE AN	@NAUTIC OCEAN	@NAUTIC OCEAN	@NAUTIC OCEAN	@NAUTIC OCEAN
CET ECI MA	@CETECIMA	@CETECIMA	@CETECIMA	@CETECIMA

MARINA FUNCHAL	https://www.facebook.com/MarinaDoFunchal/	https://twitter.com/FunchalMarina	https://www.instagram.com/marinadofunchal/	https://www.linkedin.com/in/marina-funchal/
ACIF-CCIM	@ACIF-CCIM	@ACIF-CCIM	@ACIF-CCIM	@ACIF-CCIM
DRPMAZORES	@DRPMAZORES	@DRPMAZORES	@DRPMAZORES	@DRPMAZORES
CTM	@CTM	@CTM	@CTM	@CTM
EBI	@EBI	@EBI	@EBI	@EBI

4.6 NEWSLETTER

TWINNEDBySTARS aims to keep its stakeholders informed and updated about its progress, activities, and achievements throughout the project's duration. The newsletter will be distributed to both consortium members and external subscribers, with English as the default language. The feasibility of translating the newsletter into other project partner languages (French, Portuguese and Spanish) will be evaluated by the Consortium, and if applicable each partner will assume responsibility for its translation. The design of the newsletter will align with the project's visual identity and will be made available in both HTML and PDF formats. The newsletters will be sent to the contact lists. On the website, a form will be placed so that users can fill it out in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). On the other hand, a newsletter's dedicated section will be developed on the website to ensure access to and availability for all online visitors. To compile each newsletter edition, active participation from partners is essential. Partners contributions are requested two weeks prior to the scheduled release of each newsletter.

The newsletter will also include updates on upcoming events, trainings, workshops, and conferences related to the project, as well as new publications and other relevant information. It is important to note that the content for the newsletter will be drawn from the communication and dissemination material prepared throughout the project, ensuring that it is aligned with the overall project goals and strategies.

Table 8. Provisional calendar for newsletters' release.

Nº	Main contents	Contribution by partners	Estimated release of newsletter
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project presentation ✓ Expected outcomes ✓ Meet the consortium ✓ First Project News, Events & Performed activities ✓ TWINNEDBySTARS in the media 	1 st February 2024	15 th February 2024

2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project News & Results ✓ TWINNEDBySTARS in the media ✓ Future events 	30 th August 2024	30 th September 2024
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project News & Results ✓ TWINNEDBySTARS in the media ✓ Future events 	1 st March 2025	31 st March 2025
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project News & Results ✓ TWINNEDBySTARS in the media ✓ Future events 	30 th August 2025	30 th September 2025
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project News & Results ✓ D&C Activities report ver.2 summary ✓ Demonstration video ✓ TWINNEDBySTARS in the media Future events 	1 st March 2026	31 st March 2026
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Main conclusions of the project and impacts ✓ Storytelling video ✓ Sustainability & Legacy ✓ Conclusions from final conference 	30 th August 2026	30 th September 2026

4.6.1 CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT AND GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION

To register for the TWINNEDBySTARS project newsletter, stakeholders are invited to use the subscription box available on the project's website, specifically in the 'home' and 'news' section. The newsletter distribution follows the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines and is facilitated through a dedicated Customer Relationship Management software, such as [Wordpress plug-in](#), ensuring compliance and data protection. All newsletters will be published in a dedicated section hosted on the TWINNEDBySTARS website.

4.6.2 INDIVIDUAL RIGHTS and consent

Individuals who subscribe to the TWINNEDBySTARS newsletter and register for meetings or events enter their email address, which is required for newsletter delivery, as well as additional optional information. TWINNEDBySTARS will notify subscribers ahead of time about the purpose and use of their data. In compliance with GDPR regulations, CE, as the partner responsible for TWINNEDBySTARS 's communication and dissemination activities, will process subscribers' data lawfully and fairly. Appropriate technical and organisational security measures will be implemented to safeguard the data, solely for the purpose of newsletter distribution and to generate anonymous and aggregated statistics upon request from the European Commission. Personal data collected will be stored safely by CE and will not be shared with other consortium members or external stakeholders.

To promote newsletter subscriptions, the invitation will be advertised on the project website and various social media channels. All consortium partners will be encouraged to invite selected international and local stakeholders to subscribe. Additional methods for promotion may include featuring the opt-in link on Facebook, Twitter/X, LinkedIn and Instagram, promoting the newsletter during TWINNEDBySTARS events, incorporating social media campaigns and subscription options in registration forms, and designing banners for publication on various websites, including partner sites and other digital channels such as the QR codes.

Subscription to the newsletter is voluntary, and recipients will have the option to unsubscribe at any time using the provided opt-out link in each issue. For the TWINNEDBySTARS project, it is essential to have a legal basis, namely consent, to process personal data in the newsletter database. Therefore, the project relies on voluntary, specific, informed, and unambiguous consent from subscribers. A written record will be maintained to verify that proper consent has been obtained, clearly indicating when and how individuals have agreed to the processing of their personal data. Consent will be explicit and require clear affirmative action, ensuring transparency by using straightforward language and removing pre-ticked consent boxes.

4.7 PRESS RELEASE

Several press releases will be published in the TWINNEDBySTARS' website and in the different partners' websites. All these publications will be related to the events or crucial announcement from TWINNEDBySTARS such as the Kick-Off meeting or specific events in the field of marine-base tourism, as for example, "Fimar 2024" or International Fairs as "SeaTech Canarias" in Canary Islands. These press releases will be mainly created by CE.

CE will create them for TWINNEDBySTARS key events and milestones and share with the Consortium for their communication responsible to adapt them. The process for approval of press releases is the following:

- 1) The press releases will be ready by the CE team **one week in advance** to the event or announcement date.
- 2) It will be then **shared to the Consortium** for their review so they can send any feedback or changes desired to CE.
- 3) The **final version** will be sent **one or two days before** the event to each partner's press services to adapt it and share it on the day of the event.

Furthermore, each partner should get in touch to CE when they are releasing a press release related to any of the actions planned in the project or, in general, with TWINNEDBySTARS.

It is vital to show consistency in the D&C of TWINNEDBySTARS's results. Thus, the partners' press office should check that the style agreed by the Consortium is thoroughly followed. An example of this can be to always write **TWINNEDBySTARS** instead of TWINNEDBySTARS.

4.8 VIDEOS

Throughout the project, in order to express the objectives of TWINNEDBySTARS in a clearer and more visual way, and reach a greater number of people, a series of videos will be produced. They will be produced to help raise public awareness of the potential of marine-based and coastal eco-tourism, circular economy and innovation. They will explain the importance of the EU support to this type of initiatives and bring about the main TWINNEDBySTARS messages outlined. Some videos will be more focused on storytelling, involving project partners and representatives of the quadruple helix, particularly the involved enterprises.

These videos will be produced in the following way:

- An animated video will be released to use it as a key promotional tool for the project.
- Additional short videos with testimonies from partners and stakeholders, as well as reporting on implemented activities such as co-creation workshops, will be released.

The videos will be produced in English and, in some case, with subtitles in the three languages of the Consortium (Spanish, Portuguese, French). These videos will be uploaded to TWINNEDBySTARS social media channels and distributed across partners' channels. The animated video will be also housed on the project website's homepage, while the rest of the videos will be placed in [the video section](#) of the TWINNEDBySTARS website

5. EVENTS AND CONFERENCES

5.1 ORGANISATION OF EVENTS

The project's budget covers partner's participation in international conferences, fairs, seminars, distributed across the project duration. These events are effective ways of reaching out to various stakeholders, making them key components of the TWINNEDBySTARS Project's dissemination activities.

The participation of project partners in such events will enhance the project's visibility and engagement with stakeholders and other European projects. Consortium partners are encouraged to participate in events they consider relevant for disseminating the project. At the same time, the project will ensure the organisation of dedicated dissemination events/webinars, and it will support in the promotion of events planned in WP2 (trainings) and WP3 (co-creation workshops).

In addition, WP5 will regularly publish potential physical or virtual events aligned with the dissemination strategy and promote relevant news on social media and the project website. WP5 Leader, CE, with the support of project partners, will periodically map out events. Likewise, WP1 will draw up a list of potential fairs (D1.1) to promote the selected project product from WP3. Finally, partners are requested to inform CE about dedicated events their organisations are planning to organise or attend at the EU/national level.

Particular attention will be given to monitoring gender in the project events organized. The evaluation reports of each event will include the monitoring on the number of women participants.

5.1.1 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT EVENTS

A stakeholder engagement plan and an internationalisation plan will be in place to serve as roadmaps for integrating key representatives of the quadruple helix into the TWINNEDBySTARS events. Based on the stakeholder engagement plan from WP1, and in conjunction with WP5, a set of diverse activities will be organised tailored to each type of organizations, including interviews, focus groups, workshops, matchmaking activities, etc.

These activities will include, among others:

- Presentations & networking at relevant local / regional / national / international events
- Dedicated workshops for a focused engagement with specific target groups (industry and civil society)
- Citizen science initiatives in collaboration with the CMC and ULPGC
- Interviews
- Focus groups
- Technical workshops and trainings
- Policy making events

Initial activities will be carried out to set the basis for the next project tasks, including analysing the existing cooperation networks in the field of maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs in order to identify and engage the most relevant stakeholder networks in line with the TWINNEDBySTARS initiative.

The task 1.1 will also involve a mapping of the actors of the quadruple helix, by identifying them in each of the archipelagos, as well as at national, European and international level in collaboration with WP5 and developing a stakeholder engagement plan as a complement to the communication actions of the project.

5.1.2 TRAINING EVENTS

A capacity building programme will be implemented with tourism firms and other relevant stakeholders under WP2, to increase awareness, motivation, skills, and provide them with tools to accelerate digital and ecological transition, and to identify opportunities for open and innovation with actors from other ORs.

The aim is to increase awareness, motivation, skills and provide tools to tourism firms and decision makers in the context of coastal and maritime tourism, to accelerate digital and ecological transition, and transnational cooperation in the ORs.

- 1) **Co-design of the training programme:** a call and selection of companies participating in the training programmes of each of the regions will be carried out.
- 2) **Training & practical workshops** will be implemented in the 4 ORs to serve to reinforce knowledge, concepts, information and data, and analysis of successful experiences. Other work sessions will be held to increase creativity, conflict resolution, multi-criteria decision techniques and cost-benefit analysis, aspects that will be transversal to all training modules. The programme will be certified as professional training by ULPGC-TIDES. At the same time, it will be possible to adapt and improve existing tools for self-diagnosis in competitiveness, carbon footprint, digital maturity, innovation potential, and circular economy, which would be made available to the entire business network in the regions, with the help of public actors.
- 3) The participating companies will go through a personalized process of **self-evaluation**, analysis of actions for improvements and definition of the best pathways for the ecological and digital innovation transition, with support of experts.

5.1.3 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

There will be at least 1 international conference. This will coincide with the end of the project. Thus, this international conference will also be the Final conference where results and main conclusions will be presented. The estimated date for this conference ranges from Month 33 to Month 35 (June 2026 to August 2026).

5.2 ASSISTANCE TO OTHER EVENTS

5.2.1 MAPPING OF EVENTS

A mapping of most relevant events will be performed throughout the project duration. The participation of project partners to other events is of utmost importance in order to exploit synergies and reach a wider number of stakeholders. CE will provide regularly a list of relevant events in order for project partners to consider their availability and interest in attending.

In particular, synergies with other EU funded projects will be sought. Events will be mapped to ensure participation of TWINNEDBySTARS to display its exhibition stand, infographics, videos and other project activities. An initial list of events is proposed below, and it will be updated and expanded on a regular basis, also complemented by inputs from WP1 in relation to fairs:

Marine-maritime sector:

- FIMAR (Sea's International Fair) May 2024
- Global Maritime Congress (May 20-21, 2024) Turkey
- NAUTICAMPO Salão Internacional de Navegação de Recreio, Desporto Aventura, Caravanismo e Piscinas (17-21 April 2024), Lisbon, Portugal

Innovation:

- SeaTech Canarias (Int. Summit of technological innovation in the marine-maritime sector) Nov 2023
- SeaTech week, 15-17 October 2024 (Brest, France)

Blue economy:

- Annual European Maritime Days (EMD)
- EU Ocean Days
- Biannual European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference
- Innovazul: II International Meeting of Knowledge and Blue Economy
- International Ocean Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)

Before and after attending an event, the partners should contact CE indicating the title of the event, place, and date, as well as any supporting documents such as power point presentations, videos and pictures of the event. More details on this are available under D5.1 Consortium Agreement and Management Plan delivered on month 3.

When partners attend an event, but it is not possible to present TWINNEDBySTARS, partners are invited to mention at least the participation of their organization in the project and invite event attendants to visit the [TWINNEDBySTARS project website](#).

5.2.2 REGIONAL / NATIONAL / EU EVENTS

The participation of partners in national, European and international events will be promoted, paying special attention to conferences organized in the consortium countries (France, Portugal Belgium and Spain). TWINNEDBySTARS will participate in at least **10 regional, national or EU events** during the course of the project but a higher participation is recommended and expected. For these events partners are expected to prepare exhibition stands to promote TWINNEDBySTARS and its results.

6. PRESS OFFICE

The communication actions of the press office include different activities according to the stipulated schedule. To attract the attention of the media, both at regional, national, and international level, the communication actions to be implemented are:

- Drafting and sending press releases and dissemination of newsworthy topics related to the project, the events carried out and the planned communication actions.
- Elaboration of a specific media database, paying special attention to the local and regional media, as well as specialised media such as digital newspapers (INFOPUERTOS,

- CABI Digital Library, NauticaPress, Portugal Náutico) and agencies (EFE, EUROPAPRESS, REUTERS, AFP, LUSA).
- Management of interviews with participants and speakers on radio, press and television. Preparation of own interviews with participants, partners, and collaborators.
 - Drafting and sending out press releases for planned project events. Organisation of official and technical press conferences.
 - Coordination with press and protocol offices of public institutions from the consortium.
 - Reinforcement tasks, by means of email marketing and telephone calls, as well as confirmation of attendance at press conferences and reception of press releases.
 - Providing the media with permanent download links to the photographic and audiovisual material generated on the different events planned, thanks to the implementation of a dedicated server or through the website.
 - Sending infographics, photographic, and audiovisual material, and other project outputs such as the expected handout to the media via corporate e-mail as a complement to the server.
 - Informative and logistical assistance for the needs of the media covering the planned events, press conferences and actions.
 - Permanent contact with journalists, as well as on-site assistance on their arrival to the onsite events. Provision of an update service for all the information generated.
 - Compilation of the impact generated in the media (agencies, written and digital press, radio and television) and preparation of clippings.
 - Updating of the media list, registration of new contacts, systematisation and conversion into a database.
 - Preparation of the final communication report.

The generation of content, writing and dissemination of press releases from a dedicated communications office is essential for the international, national, and local media, both general and specialized, to have regular information on the actions to be carried out, covering the whole project, thus maintaining a greater presence in search engines on a regular basis.

7. MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

Research data will especially be gathered within work packages 1, 2 and 3. Considering all the information generated in the framework of the project, an efficient knowledge management including the management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) should be an integral part of the overall project management structure. Otherwise, arrangements to be considered and established in the CA relevant for IP management should cover aspects such as knowledge management, confidentiality obligations, background, ownership, and transfer of ownership of results, protection and exploitation of results, dissemination, access rights, settlement of disputes, among others. More detailed information about data management might be found on the data management plan.

Since CE manages information generated within the project, especially through its publication on the website, it is vital to highlight some aspects related to IP in the digital age. When setting up a website, it is necessary to be aware of a couple of potential pitfalls and issues related to IP. When looking at our rapidly evolving digital world, questions related to copyright and how to protect content online have been at the forefront of discussions for long. Just because something is online does not mean it is copyright free. The following list sums up the most important aspects considered when going online on the website:

- Domain name: TWINNEDBySTARS.eu was registered successfully, also paying attention to avoiding getting in the way of third party's trademark.

- Most of designs elements used on the website are free of use, such as icons or fonts. Also, CE has the license to freely use original designs from WordPress as well as other designs under Envato Elements of Freepik license certificates as well as other software such as Canva Pro and Adobe Creative Cloud.
- Project trademark and logo are included on the website. Also, other trademarks and logos are included with appropriate authorisation, for example, partner’s logos.
- Copyright. All original images, videos, and music included on the TWINNEDBySTARS website are protected by copyright. Most licenses provided through paid repositories (Freepik, Envato, Canva).

8. SYNERGIES AND NETWORKING

Task 5.2 “Dissemination activities” deals with promoting synergies with other funded projects to foster synergies in knowledge transfer and in exploitation of TWINNEDBySTARS.

8.1 OBJECTIVES AND PRESENTATION

To achieve the objectives set for this project and ensure a good dissemination of its results, special attention is given to the creation of a network of activities. The partners of the TWINNEDBySTARS project get in touch with companies, entities, higher education institutions and related projects and create synergies with the key actors in the field of marine and maritime ecotourism, innovation and circular economy.

These entities either work with marine solutions or study them, for marine solutions development.

In addition, it is also vital to create synergies with European projects and platforms that deal with the abovementioned sectors. Special attention will be given to knowledge transfer between sister projects.

8.2 SISTER PROJECTS

One of the main target groups of objectives for the creation of networks and synergies consists of other projects related to CINEA or EMFAF projects, as well as other projects financed by the EU. It is about cooperating with project consortia to share the latest information and talk about common issues. EU experts from respective fields of interest will also be contacted to improve and harmonize the general knowledge in these fields and improve its dissemination.

Below there is a table with projects that are most similar and complementary to TWINNEDBySTARS and that have been already contacted for creating synergies and networking:

Table 9. List of key projects to start creating synergies with.

PROJECT	DESCRIPTION
ECOROUTE	ecoRoute proposes to design and implement a multidimensional and integrated approach fostering smart UW Cultural & Nature Tourism (UCNT) offer in the participating Outermost Regions, enabling their transformation to smart UCNT Destinations, with a new ecological focus that draws on natural and cultural resources, diversifying and developing smart UCNT services for the benefit of both residents and visitors. ecoRoute expected outcomes and impacts include the addressing of seasonality into tourism planning, extending the tourism season from 6 to almost 12 months; the support of existing tourism value chains to bloom and new ones to emerge in sustainable cultural tourism.

CALLMEBLUE	CALLMEBLUE aims to strengthen existing maritime clusters alliances in the Mediterranean area in order to accelerate north-south regional cooperation processes towards the emergence of strategic maritime clusters in North Africa area (south-south cooperation). The project will aim to create a strategic vision and transferable models of interregional cooperation, by implementing concrete actions at both local and regional level in order to raise awareness on the relevance of Maritime clusters as key actors for sustainable blue economy policies such as promoting exchange of best practices and knowledge transfer between north and southern area.
FISATUR	The FISATUR PROJECT is directed to likeminded fishery and tourism sectors to achieve coastal fishing regions' proper economic growth through the integration and promotion of innovative Atlantic tourist products and services linked to the fishing and maritime heritage. The project will contribute to assess the effectiveness of a fishing tourism model that can help spreading an innovative way to think and use the coastal resources. The best two ideas per country obtained in the incubator will participate in trade mission navigation route from Portugal to France with strategic stops where visits and exchange (B2B) will be held with other network initiatives.

Beyond these three key sister projects from the EMFAF programme, WP5 activities under TWINNEDBySTARS will seek to engage other funded projects under Horizon Europe or Interreg, or at national level, as well as to identify potential synergies with other existing EU-based initiatives such as the Charter of the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters. This will be part of the regular monitoring activities performed by CE and EBI.

8.3 PARTNERS' NETWORKING ACTIVITIES

All partners are strongly encouraged to engage in networking activities with relevant initiatives, projects, or organisations at local and national level, acting as multipliers for the TWINNEDBySTARS projects.

To carry out a correct control of the contacts for the elaboration of networks, partners should gather their data in a dedicated shared excel provided by CE. WP5 leader will also regularly remind partners to share the network with them. At the same time, the partners that participate in a networking activity are invited to study the possibilities of synergies and collaborations. This can be carried out in various ways, such as:

- Exchange of links on the respective website.
- Exchange of good practices.
- Sharing of public deliverables and other outputs.
- Information on events and activities promoted by TWINNEDBySTARS.
- Invitation of Coordinators/Partners of other projects as speakers at TWINNEDBySTARS events, webinars and/or project meetings.
- Organization of joint events or activities.

After having engaged in a networking activity, partners are kindly asked to fill in the shared excel form that will be provided by CE indicating in the relevant column the type of future collaboration which has been suggested.

9. CONTINGENCY PLANS

To be prepared in the case of an impossibility to carry out an in-person event, to avoid unnecessary flights in consideration with the climate crisis and to ensure the maximum attendance of the partners and other stakeholders, an online platform will be used for online meetings. Priority will be given to the use of the Teams platform in the face of possible situations derived from covid-19 and/or other events.

Special consideration will be given to organizing hybrid events to give all partners and stakeholders the possibility of participating both on-site and online.

The chosen software for this will be Teams, both for informal calls, steering committees, bilateral meetings and webinars. Below an array of **supporting tools** for the organization of online or hybrid events are provided:

Table 10. Supporting tools for online photo exhibitions.

D&C / Engagement objectives	CHANNELS
Showcase experience & promote visibility	Instagram
	YOUPIIC
	Flickr
	Pinterest
	Behance (by Adobe)
	Vero Social
	Steller Stories

Table 11. Supporting tools for online videos.

D&C / Engagement objectives	CHANNELS	Optional ideas/notes
*Present project results & promote project visibility	Youtube	* Videos could be used as a tool/part of an event * Creating a series of videos/event (e.g. video days/week) * Creating interaction through reacting on comments and live videos
*Enhance interaction/participation activities	Vimeo	
	DailyMotion	
	Facebook direct videos	
*Exchange views	Instagram Direct	

Table 12. Supporting tools for online quiz events.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Channels	Costs & Participants	Optional ideas/notes
*Communicate/transfer project results/insights *Promote visibility of the project	Kahoot	10€/20€/40€ p.m. - 7 days free trial / 20/50/2000	* Videos could be used as a tool/part of an event * Creating a series of videos/event (e.g. video days/week)
	Quizizz	Free / -	
	Socrative	free / 99\$ p.a. / 5000 / 10000	

*Encourage interaction	Typeform	30€/70€	* Creating interaction through reacting on comments and live videos
	Slido	Free / 3 polls per event / 1000 participants	

Table 13. Supporting tools for creative competitions / social media challenges.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Ideas/notes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Showcase experiences * Promote visibility of the project * Encourage interaction * Exchange views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Participants create input referring to a given topic/task * Social media as platform / supportive social media wall/liveblog * Awarding the participants action (e.g. best video, picture, story etc.) * Creating viral effects / using, chain letters & hashtags * Creating own input to showcase experiences * Launching Quizzes

Table 14. Supporting tools for creative online workshops.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Ideas/notes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Showcase experiences *Promote visibility of the project *Promote rural regions & regional projects *Exchange views and promote interaction/participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Delivering input through introduction/moderation *Promoting and exchanging specific know-how, products and projects on marine-based and coastal tourism. *Using Facebook direct videos or webinar-tools *Social media wall/liveblog to promote the event

Table 15. Supporting tools for virtual open-door day/fair.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Channels	Optional ideas/notes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate/transfer project results/insights Showcase experiences Exchange views/get feedback on project activities/results Exchange best practices/lessons learned Foster networking and interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media Direct videos and interaction via Facebook and Instagram 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Idea: Project partners + chosen stakeholders present their work/results/projects * Switching the perspective * Social media wall/liveblog

Table 16. Supporting tools for virtual summits.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Channels	Costs	Optional ideas/notes
Communicate/transfer project results/insights Showcase experiences Exchange views/get feedback on project activities/results Exchange best practices/lessons learned Foster networking and interaction Brainstorm on ideas and solutions	Virtual Summits	85€ p.m./ 14 days free trial	* Liveblog about the summit.
	Voxr	250€ / free up to 20 participants	

Table 17. Supporting online tools for webinars.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Platform	Costs & Participants	Optional ideas/notes
Communicate/transfer project results/insights Inform on latest policy initiatives/research results Showcase experiences Exchange best practices/lessons learned Get feedback on project activities	Microsoft Teams	Professional: 3,64€ p.m. (essentials) / 5,45€ (basic) / 11,37€ (standard)	*Webinars could be used as a tool/part of an event. e.g. webinar days (different webinars and moderators during a period of days) *Creating interaction through Q&A rounds, Audience *Response Systems (e.g. Polling Tools) Provide extra material, such as transcripts, slides, handouts et
	GoToMeeting	Professional: 10,75€ (12€) / 14,33€ (17€) p.m. / 14 days free / 150 / 250 participants	
	GoToWebinar	89€ / 199€ / 429€ p.m. / 100 / 500 / 1000	
	Zoom	Basic / Pro / Business: free (only 40min. per call) 13,99€ / 18,99€ p.m / 100 / 100 / 300	
	fastviewer	38€ p.m. / 30 days free / 100	
	Skype	Free, 50 participants	
	Edudip	34€ / 69€ / 139€ / 244€ p.m. / 30 / 100 / 500 / 1000	
	Adobe Connect	46€ / 120€ / 432€ / 34€ p.m. – Free trial 25 / 100 / 500 / 1000	
	Webex	Free basic version starter / plus / enterprise: 12,85€ / 17,30€ / 25,65€ 50/ 100 / 200	
	Jitsi	Free (open source) / 200 pax	
Poll Everywhere	Free / 25 participants 109€ p.a. / 700		

	SurveyMonkey	Free / 40 answers / 39€ p.m / unlimited
	Slido	Free / 3 polls per event / 1000 participants
	Mentimeter	Free / 2 questions / 5 quizzes per session 9,99€ / unlimited

Table 18. Supporting tools for online podcasts.

D&C / Engagement objectives	Channels	Costs	Optional ideas/notes
Inform on specific topics, on latest initiatives	Youtube	Free + no host needed	*Podcasts could be used as a tool/part of an event
	Soundcloud	Basic version free + no host needed / Premium: 11€ p.m	
	iTunes	Free / host needed	*Creating a series of podcasts/event (e.g. podcast days/week)
	Spotify	Free / host needed	
	Host		
	Podigee	15-29€ p.m./ 30 days free trial	*Creating interaction through reacting on comments and live podcasts
	Libsyn	5-40\$ p.m	
	Captivate	19-99\$ p.m. / 7 days free trial	

10. MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

10.1 MONITORING OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

WP5 deals with the monitoring and evaluation of D&C activities. These will be monitored to ensure they are properly implemented and concretely support the maximization of the project's expected impacts. Monitoring the D&C activities allows in fact to assess if the actions planned are carried out properly and on time and to measure their effectiveness. Based on monitoring results, the Plan might be thus reformulated to improve communication and dissemination outreach.

To monitor the project, partners are periodically requested to provide information on the activities carried out (for instance organization of events, publications of news/press releases, etc., presentations at conferences) while CE is in charge of monitoring and reporting on the use of the website, social media, and on the events whose organization is under CE's responsibility. Based on the reports submitted by the partners, CE can formulate recommendations for the future dissemination and communication activities.

Table 19 presents the different monitoring and evaluation activities to be performed, the schedule and the responsibility of partners.

Table 19. Monitoring and evaluation activities.

Communication activity / tool	Indicators/data	Schedule frequency monitoring / of	Responsible partner
Website and social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Number of visits *Number of posts *Number of cross-linking 	*Biannual	CE
Participation in other events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Title of the event *Place and date *Number of attendants *Description of participation and press release when applicable *Pictures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *All information to be filled/sent one week prior *Pictures to be sent the day or the day after for communication purposes 	Project partner
TWINNEDBySTARS' events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Press release, title of the event, place and date, number of attendants (signature list), description of the participation *Pictures *Number of posts related to the event, satisfaction questionnaire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Information to be filled/sent two weeks prior *Pictures to be sent the day or the day after for *Number of posts and satisfaction questionnaire to within 1 month following the even 	Partner responsible for the organization of the event
Dissemination report on communication and dissemination activities performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Name of the partner *Name of press release published *N° of news published on the partner's website *N° of scientific articles *N° of local/national events attended *N° of international events attended *N° of appearances in local media (radio, tv, newspaper) 	Biannual	Project partner

10.2 MONITORING ON PARTNERS' DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

When exploiting synergies and reaching a wider number of stakeholders is key that project partners participate to other events and disseminate project information and results in events

such as external events, dissemination publication actions in external websites, newsletters, local radio and conference articles.

A continuous monitoring of the dissemination activities made by project partners is carried out within WP5 tasks. An excel file will be provided by CE to all partners in order to keep records of the press releases, articles, and events, gathering the information based on:

- The partner who carried out the activity.
- The date which the activity took place in.
- Activity outreach.
- Publication source.
- URL link to the activity results or proof.
- Targeted audience.
- In case of an event, the type of event, location, and general information.

10.3 EVALUATION OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In conjunction with the monitoring, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities will be performed periodically mainly using a set of indicators of success, including those targets set in the Grant Agreement and reported in the table below. The continuous monitoring will allow CE to assess the evolution and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities and evaluate any corrections or preventive measures to increase the reach-out of WP5 activities.

Table 20. Monitoring and evaluation indicators.

Communication activity / results	Indicators	Target
Events	*Participation of regional/national/EU events *Organisation of events	*Participation to 10 events *Organisation of 10 events/webinars/masterclasses for civil society, policy makers, and/or industry
Newsletter	*Production of newsletter *Subscribers	*6 newsletters *300 subscribers
Press releases	N° of press releases	At least 9 press releases
Project website	Site visits	Total 3000 site visits
Publications	N° of peer reviewed publications	At least 1 scientific publication
Social media	Followers (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook, Instagram)	1000 followers
Videos	N° of videos produced	1 animated video and at least 10 short videos / reels

11. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

To engage with identified stakeholder groups during the project duration, WP5 activities rely on a range of essential tools. These tools include visual identity, promotional materials, website, which are described in the following sections:

11.1 ROLL UP

Figure 3. Roll-up.

The roll up is 85cm x 200cm and has been distributed to partners to be utilized in the dissemination activities.

11.2 LEAFLET

A leaflet has been developed to provide a brief and comprehensive overview of the project's objectives in triptych format with the dimensions of an A4 size sheet. It is a valuable tool for disseminating the project's activities and outcomes, increasing awareness and engagement among stakeholders, and promoting synergies and networking with complementary initiatives. Its design may vary over the lifespan of the project. The following figure represents the first version of the leaflet which will be progressively adapted over the lifespan of the project:

Figure 4. Leaflet.

11.3 WEBSITE

This website is put online in January 2024 (M4), thus complying with the WP5 milestone according to which the website needs to be launched online by M6.

The homepage of the TWINNEDBySTARS website features a clean and modern design, with a prominent header that includes the project logo and menu. The main content area of the homepage features a slider with high-quality images and short descriptions of the project created to communicate the overall objective of TWINNEDBySTARS, along with links to more information.

Below the slider, there are sections that highlight key project descriptions and news and events, with links to more detailed information. The frontend of the www.TWINNEDBySTARS.eu website is developed using modern web technologies, specifically HTML, CSS and JavaScript. The website uses a responsive design approach, which means it adjusts its layout and content to fit different screen sizes, from large desktops to small mobile devices. This makes the website accessible to a wider public, regardless of the device they are using to access it.

In particular, the frontend of the www.TWINNEDBySTARS.eu website is being developed with a focus on user experience and accessibility, using modern web technologies and a responsive design approach. The website features a clean and modern design with intuitive navigation and clear calls to action, making it easy for users to find the information they need and engage with the project.

- HOME
 - General information about the project.

Figure 5. Website "Home".

- Social media direct access and latest publications.

Figure 6. Website "Social media".

- Newsletter box to subscribe to the newsletter.

Figure 7. Website “Newsletter box”.

- ABOUT
 - Main information regarding the project.

Objectives of TWINNEDbySTARS:

- Strengthening and sustaining cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism within the outermost regions. This involves linking the quadruple helix and ensuring network homogeneity through the promotion of certifications (quality, tourism, environmental, Starlight), participating in international fairs under the "Trade Winds Starlight Adventure," and promoting a unified brand image.
- Upskilling and capacity building for tourism firms and stakeholders in coastal and maritime tourism. This includes fostering circular economy practices, facilitating digital transition, promoting networking, and encouraging innovation.
- Creating new spaces for the co-creation of innovative products and nautical tourism experiences. This encompasses activities such as star tourism, marine ecotourism, sustainable Atlantic crossing using trade winds, and the application of virtual reality.

The Challenge

Tourism tends to focus on popular destinations rather than remote ones, leading to overexploitation of these areas. In the context of coastal and maritime tourism, this can harm biodiversity, local communities, and their culture.

Figure 8. Website "About".

- **Work Packages.** Inside the project tab you can find all WP explained with images and results updated.

WP1 | Leader: CMC
Strengthening and sustainability of cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the outermost regions

WP1 analyses maritime and coastal tourism networks in the Atlantic OR, maps the actors and involves the stakeholders. Standardise certifications and promote digitisation and the circular economy. It also creates internationalisation and legacy plans to support cooperation and product development.

WP2 | Leader: ULPGC – TIDES
Upskilling and capacity building

WP2 aims to establish a capacity-building for coastal and maritime tourism to boost digital and ecological transition, fostering transnational cooperation among ORs. Aim is to equip tourism firms and decision-makers with skills, tools, and motivation for circular practices, efficiency, and biodiversity protection.

WP3 | Leader: NAUTIC OCEAN
Generation of new spaces for co-creation of new products and new nautical tourism experiences

WP3 focuses on creating joint working groups with entrepreneurs in the coastal and maritime tourism sectors to foster co-creation and generate new tourism products. Objectives include analysing existing products, creating spaces for co-creation, and developing joint products in areas like star tourism, marine ecotourism, and sustainable Atlantic crossings using virtual reality. The final goal is to test at least one product and create a marketing and business plan for it.

Figure 9. Website "work packages".

WP4 | Leader: FCPTC – ULPGC
Coordination and Management

The project will provide regular updates on its progress and outcomes through mandatory reports submitted to the European Commission, including both interim and final reports. In addition to these, periodic management reports will be compiled, encompassing: i) a concise summary of activities undertaken in previous periods and an assessment of advancements; ii) detailed plans for upcoming months at the task level, with possible adjustment proposals if needed; iii) an updated catalog of submitted and published publications, as well as presentations of project results.

WP5 | Leader: CE
Communication & Dissemination

WP5 is responsible for developing a dissemination and communication plan outlining target groups, channels, tools and activities, which is updated regularly. It creates materials and tools for the project, including a website, logo, posters and content for social media. Promotes events, webinars, workshops and collaborations with other projects. Organises events, webinars, workshops and awareness-raising activities to engage society.

- **NEWS AND EVENTS**

Figure 10. Website “NEWS”.

Figure 11. Website “EVENTS”.

- PARTNERS

Figure 12. Website "Our CONSORTIUM".

- CONTACTS

Figure 13. Website "Contacts".

11.4 SOCIAL MEDIA

TWINNEDBySTARS can be followed on Twitter/X, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn. These accounts have been created and will be updated regularly during the project with information on project results, partners, events organized, interviews, other relevant project’s events, results and information. To this date (January 2024) these are the accounts and their posts and followers:

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/TWINNEDBySTARS/>

- User: @TWINNEDBySTARS
- Followers: 51
- Posts:77

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/TWINNEDBySTARS/>

- User: @TWINNEDBySTARS
- Followers: 207
- Posts: 77

Twitter: <https://x.com/TWINNEDBySTARS>

- User: @TWINNEDBySTARS
- Followers: 96
- Posts: 89

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/twinned-by-stars/>

User: TWINNEDBySTARS Project

Followers: 237

Posts: 83

11.5 HASHTAGS

Hashtags are a way to disseminate and communicate information on most social media platforms. To expand their reach and take advantage of current trends, TWINNEDBySTARS will utilise different hashtags to categorise similar content and connect their project with others. By doing so, it will be easier to organise group related content, and hashtags can encourage engagement among individuals.

Table 15 below lists the created hashtags that can be used in addition to those that connect with FLIARA's own media content.

Table 21. Monitoring and evaluation indicators.

Trending and media hashtags	
#TWINNEDBySTARSEU	#nautical
#EMFAF	#maritime
#CINEA	#ecotourism
#TWINNEDBySTARSEU	#MarineEcotourism
#outermostregion	#Sustainability
	#Innovation

	#ClimateAction #BeGreenGoBlue #MaritimeExploration
--	--

CONCLUSIONS

The TWINNEDBySTARS project's Plan for dissemination and communication presents a comprehensive and strategic approach to raise awareness and promote the project's objectives. The plan outlines various channels to promote the project, including print and digital media, social media platforms, and different methods for disseminating the project, for example engaging target groups through both online and offline activities.

One of the primary goals of the plan is to inform the public about this European Commission-funded initiative. The approach intends to instill trust and promote collaboration among stakeholders by efficiently communicating information about consortium members and the overall objective of the project. Furthermore, it seeks to create opportunities for active participation from end users and interested parties, facilitating their engagement, collaboration and involvement.

To ensure a consistent and recognizable public image for the project, various communication tools such as promotional materials and website are designed, contributing to a cohesive visual identity, and reinforcing the project's message. The plan also incorporates a comprehensive set of monitoring and evaluation indicators to assess the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication efforts, enabling continuous improvement and adaptation as needed.

An essential aspect of the plan is the establishment of partnerships with complementary projects and initiatives. This approach maximizes the impact and sustainability of the project's outcomes and results while also enhancing the visibility of ecotourism innovations and practices in EU ORs.

This D&C plan is considered a lively document as the project D&C strategy will be periodically assessed and, if needed, fine-tuned or updated based on the project's progression and outcomes.

TWINNED

By Stars

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101124900. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.